

Effective Dominating Energy in Neutrosophic Over Graphs

E. Lincy ^{1,*} and V. Maheswari ²

¹ Research Scholar Reg. No.: 23212012092001, lincy.jc@gmail.com
PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.P.C. Mahalaxmi College for Women, Thoothukudi-628002, Tamil Nadu, India
Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012, Tamil Nadu, India.

² Assistant Professor; mahiraj2005@gmail.com
PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.P.C. Mahalaxmi College for Women, Thoothukudi-628002, Tamil Nadu, India
Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627012, Tamil Nadu, India.

* Correspondence: lincy.jc@gmail.com; Tel.: +91 9442218967

Abstract: In neutrosophic set, three component values t, i, f are restricted to $[0,1]$. Considering numerous instances and practical uses, neutrosophic set is extended neutrosophic overset which contains no elements with neutrosophic component less than zero and at least one element with neutrosophic component larger than one by Smarandache[1]. Neutrosophic over graphs (NovGs) were defined by combining neutrosophic over sets with graphs. R. Narmada Devi et.al.[2] introduced domination in a neutrosophic over graph, which is expressed in terms of effective edges between the vertices. Utilizing this concept, the effective dominating matrix of NovG is determined and the effective dominating energy in NovGs is discussed in the present study. The characteristics of effective domination and dominating energy in neutrosophic over graphs are further examined.

Keywords: neutrosophic graph, neutrosophic over sets, neutrosophic over graph, effective dominating matrix, effective dominating energy.

1. Introduction

The fuzzy set (FS), which has membership degree for each element, was first presented by L. Zadeh [3] in 1965. In 1986, K. Atanassov established intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) on universe X in [4], where non-membership degree $\nu_A(x) \in [0,1]$, was considered in addition to membership degree $\mu_A(x) \in [0,1]$ such that $\forall x \in X, \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$. In his 1995 manuscript, which was issued in 1998, Smarandache [5] created neutrosophic set (NS) as elaboration of FS and IFS by including indeterminacy degree (i) as distinct element. H. Wang et.al. broadened NS to single valued neutrosophic sets in [6]. Since there are numerous instances and uses of over-, under-, and off-neutrosophic components in actual world, neutrosophic over-/under-/off-set was published in 2007 after Smarandache [7] initially defined it in 1995.

The idea of dominating sets and domination number in graphs was first proposed by Oystein Ore[8] in 1962. Cockayne and Hedetniemi first denoted the domination number as $\gamma(G)$ in [9]. The notion of domination in fuzzy graphs was proposed by A. Nagoorgani and V.T. Chandrasekaran in [10] and domination in intuitionistic fuzzy graphs was defined by R. Parvathi and G. Thamizhendi in [11] using strong arc. In [12], M. Mullai introduced domination in neutrosophic graphs(NG) and domination parameters of single valued neutrosophic graphs is analysed by R. Jahir Hussain and S.

Satham Hussain [13]. The domination in neutrosophic over graphs in terms of effective edges were established by R. Narmada devi et.al. is considered in this study.

The concept of energy is defined by Gutman [14] as absolute sum of characteristic values of graph's adjacency matrix. M.R. Rajesh Kanna [15] proposed minimum dominating energy of graph. A. Kalimulla et al. [16] and E. Kartheek & Basha [17] calculated dominating energy in FGs and IFGs, respectively. Dominating energy in NG was defined by Mullai & Broumi [18].

This article is organized according to the following: Section 2 provides a list of fundamental terms. Section 3 focusses on definitions of effective domination based on effective(eff) edges and effective dominating matrix for determining effective dominating energy in NovG. Section 4 elaborates propositions on effective domination in NovG. In section 5, an application of effective domination is discussed along with comparison of NG with NovG. Section 6 concludes the discussion.

2. Preliminaries

Definition:2.1 Take ζ as universe. NS ϱ in ζ has three functions for membership: truth (t_ϱ), indeterminacy (i_ϱ), and falsity (f_ϱ) where $t_\varrho, i_\varrho, f_\varrho$ are the real standard elements in $[0,1]$. It is stated this way:

$$\varrho = \{(\varkappa, (t_\varrho(\varkappa), i_\varrho(\varkappa), f_\varrho(\varkappa))): \varkappa \in \zeta; t_\varrho, i_\varrho, f_\varrho \in]^{-0}, 1^+ [\}$$

There is no limit on the total of $t_\varrho(\varkappa), i_\varrho(\varkappa), f_\varrho(\varkappa)$. Hence $0^- \leq t_\varrho(\varkappa) + i_\varrho(\varkappa) + f_\varrho(\varkappa) \leq 3^+$.

Definition:2.2[6] Consider Λ to as region of points where \varkappa represents generic element. SVNS \beth in Λ is determined by truth-membership function $t_\beth(\varkappa)$, indeterminacy-membership function $i_\beth(\varkappa)$, and falsity-membership function $f_\beth(\varkappa)$. Every point \varkappa in Λ has $t_\beth(\varkappa), i_\beth(\varkappa), f_\beth(\varkappa) \in [0,1]$.

Definition:2.3[1] Take $\mathfrak{S} \in \mathfrak{U}$ as NS, where \mathfrak{U} denote universe of discourse. Assume functions $t(\alpha), i(\alpha)$, and $f(\alpha)$ represent degrees of membership, indeterminate-membership, and non-membership, respectively, for the generic element $\alpha \in \mathfrak{U}$, regarding NS $\mathfrak{S} \in \mathfrak{U}$ such that $t(\alpha), i(\alpha), f(\alpha): \mathfrak{U} \rightarrow [0, \Omega]$ in which $0 < 1 < \Omega$, and Ω has been determined as over-limit, $t(\alpha), i(\alpha), f(\alpha) \in (0, \Omega)$. SVN- Overset $\mathfrak{S} = \{(\alpha, < t(\alpha), i(\alpha), f(\alpha) >): \alpha \in \mathfrak{U}\}$ is such that an element from \mathfrak{S} comprises a minimum of one neutrosophic component that exceeds 1, and none of the elements has neutrosophic component below 0.

Definition:2.4[2] A neutrosophic over graph (NovG) $\mathfrak{P} = (\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})$ is defined on crisp graph $\mathfrak{P}^* = (v, e)$, where \mathcal{M} is SVN-over set on v and \mathcal{N} is SVN-over set on $e \subseteq v \times v$, respectively, thereby

1. $t_{\mathcal{N}}(wx) \leq \min [t_{\mathcal{M}}(w), t_{\mathcal{M}}(x)]$,
2. $i_{\mathcal{N}}(wx) \leq \min [i_{\mathcal{M}}(w), i_{\mathcal{M}}(x)]$ and
3. $f_{\mathcal{N}}(wx) \geq \max [f_{\mathcal{M}}(w), f_{\mathcal{M}}(x)] \forall wx \in e \subseteq v \times v$.

Definition:2.5 A complement NovG is $\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{P})$ if

1. $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{M}) = \mathcal{M}$,
2. $t_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{N})}(ux) = [t_{\mathcal{M}}(u) \wedge t_{\mathcal{M}}(x)] - t_{\mathcal{N}}(ux)$,
3. $i_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{N})}(ux) = [i_{\mathcal{M}}(u) \wedge i_{\mathcal{M}}(x)] - i_{\mathcal{N}}(ux)$ and
4. $f_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{N})}(ux) = [f_{\mathcal{M}}(u) \vee f_{\mathcal{M}}(x)] - f_{\mathcal{N}}(ux)$, for every $ux \in e$.

Definition:2.6[2] A NovG \mathfrak{P} is said to be complete if the below conditions are met with:

1. $t_{\mathcal{N}}(rw) = \min [t_{\mathcal{M}}(r), t_{\mathcal{M}}(w)]$,
2. $i_{\mathcal{N}}(rw) = \min [i_{\mathcal{M}}(r), i_{\mathcal{M}}(w)]$ and
3. $f_{\mathcal{N}}(rw) = \max [f_{\mathcal{M}}(r), f_{\mathcal{M}}(w)]$ for every $rw \in e$.

Definition:2.7 A NovG \mathfrak{P} is said to be empty (\emptyset) if $t_{\mathcal{N}}(jm) = i_{\mathcal{N}}(jm) = f_{\mathcal{N}}(jm) = 0$ for every $jm \in \mathcal{N}$.

Definition:2.8[2] Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG. Then order of NovG, real number, given by $\wp = \langle \sum_{\sigma \in \mathfrak{v}} t_{\mathcal{M}}(\sigma), \sum_{\sigma \in \mathfrak{v}} i_{\mathcal{M}}(\sigma), \sum_{\sigma \in \mathfrak{v}} f_{\mathcal{M}}(\sigma) \rangle$ where t -order = $\sum_{\sigma \in \mathfrak{v}} t_{\mathcal{M}}(\sigma)$, i -order = $\sum_{\sigma \in \mathfrak{v}} i_{\mathcal{M}}(\sigma)$ and f -order = $\sum_{\sigma \in \mathfrak{v}} f_{\mathcal{M}}(\sigma)$.

Definition:2.9 Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG. Then \mathfrak{B} is known as

1. t -acyclic, when $\nexists t$ -path from g to c , unless $g = c \forall g, c \in \mathfrak{v}$
2. i -acyclic, when $\nexists i$ -path from g to c , unless $g = c \forall g, c \in \mathfrak{v}$
3. f -acyclic, when $\nexists f$ -path from g to c , unless $g = c \forall g, c \in \mathfrak{v}$
4. acyclic, when it is any of t -acyclic, i -acyclic and f -acyclic.

Definition:2.10 Consider $\mathfrak{B} = (\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})$ and $\mathfrak{B}' = (\mathcal{M}', \mathcal{N}')$ be NovGs. Then \mathfrak{B}' is known as spanning neutrosophic graph if $\mathfrak{v} = \mathfrak{v}'$ but $\mathfrak{e}' \subseteq \mathfrak{e}$.

Definition:2.11 Consider $\mathfrak{B} = (\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})$ be NovG. \mathfrak{B} is

1. t -forest when \mathfrak{B} is t -acyclic and \exists spanning N-graph \mathfrak{R} in which all edges not from \mathfrak{R} , there is t -path \mathbb{P} from j to n , which is stronger than $t_{\mathcal{N}}(jn)$.
2. i -forest when \mathfrak{B} is i -acyclic and \exists spanning N-graph \mathfrak{R} in which all edges not from \mathfrak{R} , there is i -path \mathbb{P} from j to n , which is stronger than $i_{\mathcal{N}}(jn)$.
3. f -forest when \mathfrak{B} is f -acyclic and \exists spanning N-graph \mathfrak{R} in which all edges not from \mathfrak{R} , there is f -path \mathbb{P} from j to n , which is stronger than $f_{\mathcal{N}}(jn)$.
4. forest when it is either t -forest, i -forest and f -forest.

Definition:2.12 Consider $\mathfrak{B} = (\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})$ be NovG. Then \mathfrak{B} is

1. t -tree when \mathfrak{B} is t -forest in which $\exists t$ -path from a to $x \forall a, x \in \mathfrak{v}$.
2. i -tree when \mathfrak{B} is i -forest in which $\exists i$ -path from a to $x \forall a, x \in \mathfrak{v}$.
3. f -tree when \mathfrak{B} is f -forest in which $\exists f$ -path from a to $x \forall a, x \in \mathfrak{v}$.
4. tree when it is either t -tree, i -tree and f -tree.

Definition:2.13[2] Consider $\mathfrak{B} = (\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})$ be NovG.

1. A series of unique vertices $p: q_0, q_1, \dots, q_x$ of length x is known as t -path if $t_{\mathcal{N}}(q_3 q_{3+1}) > 0$ for $0 \leq \mathfrak{z} \leq x - 1$. Strength of t -path, $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_t$, is $\min_{\mathfrak{z}=0}^{x-1} \{t_{\mathcal{N}}(q_3 q_{3+1})\}$.
2. A series of unique vertices $p: q_0, q_1, \dots, q_x$ of length x is known as i -path if $i_{\mathcal{N}}(q_3 q_{3+1}) > 0$ for $0 \leq \mathfrak{z} \leq x - 1$. Strength of i -path, $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_i$, is $\min_{\mathfrak{z}=0}^{x-1} \{i_{\mathcal{N}}(q_3 q_{3+1})\}$.
3. A series of unique vertices $p: q_0, q_1, \dots, q_x$ of length x is known as f -path if $f_{\mathcal{N}}(q_3 q_{3+1}) > 0$ for $0 \leq \mathfrak{z} \leq x - 1$. Strength of f -path, $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_f$, is $\min_{\mathfrak{z}=0}^{x-1} \{f_{\mathcal{N}}(q_3 q_{3+1})\}$.
4. A series of unique vertices $p: q_0, q_1, \dots, q_x$ of length x is known as path when it is t -path, i -path and f -path concurrently. Strength of path $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)$ is $\min\{\chi_{\mathcal{G}}(p)_t, \chi_{\mathcal{G}}(p)_i, \chi_{\mathcal{G}}(p)_f\}$

Definition:2.14[2] The strength between s_3 and s_l , given by $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)$, is defined as $\max\{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)_t, \chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)_i, \chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)_f\}$ where $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)_t = \max\{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_t\}$, $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)_i = \max\{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_i\}$ and $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s_3, s_l)_f = \max\{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_f\}$.

Definition:2.15 [2] An edge cd is determined as

1. t -bridge when strength of t -path from c to d discarding cd is $< t_{\mathcal{N}}(cd)$.
2. i -bridge when strength of i -path from c to d discarding cd is $< i_{\mathcal{N}}(cd)$.
3. f -bridge when strength of f -path from c to d discarding cd is $< f_{\mathcal{N}}(cd)$.
4. bridge when it is any of t -bridge, i -bridge and f -bridge.

Definition:2.16[2] An edge cd is determined as

1. t -effective(t -eff) when $t_{\mathcal{N}}(cd) > \{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}-cd}^{\infty}(c, d)_t\}$.
2. i -effective(i -eff) when $i_{\mathcal{N}}(cd) > \{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}-cd}^{\infty}(c, d)_i\}$.
3. f -effective(f -eff) when $f_{\mathcal{N}}(cd) > \{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}-cd}^{\infty}(c, d)_f\}$.

4. Effective(eff) when it is any of t -eff, i -eff and f -eff.

3. Effective dominating energy in NovG

3.1. Effective dominating set

Definition: 3.1.1 Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG and $(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{n}) \in \mathcal{N}$. A vertex \mathfrak{h} effectively dominates \mathfrak{n} if there is effective edge between them. If \mathfrak{h} dominates \mathfrak{n} , then \mathfrak{n} dominates \mathfrak{h} , hence domination is symmetric on \mathcal{N} . If $\mathfrak{h} \in \mathcal{S}$ dominates $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathcal{M}/\mathcal{S}$ by effective edge, then $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ is effective dominating (eff domi) set in \mathfrak{B} .

Definition: 3.1.2 The t -weight of vertex \mathfrak{b} is given by $\varpi_t(\mathfrak{b}) = t_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathfrak{b}) + \frac{\sum_{\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r} \text{ is } t\text{-eff edge } t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r})}{\sum_{\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r} \text{ is edge } t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r})}$. The t -weight of $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ is given by $\varpi_t(\mathcal{S}) = \sum_{\mathfrak{b} \in \mathcal{S}} (\varpi_t(\mathfrak{b}))$. If $\sum_{\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{c} \text{ is edge } t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{c})} = 0$, then we take $\frac{\sum_{\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r} \text{ is } t\text{-eff edge } t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r})}{\sum_{\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r} \text{ is edge } t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathfrak{b}\mathfrak{r})} = 0$. Let \mathcal{Z} be collection of every t -eff dominating sets in \mathfrak{B} . t -eff domination number is provided by $\gamma_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{\mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{Z}} (\varpi_t(\mathcal{S}))$. The t -dominating set with the least $\gamma_{\mathcal{S}_t}(\mathfrak{B})$ is t -eff dominating set. In the same way, we can define i -eff and f -eff dominating sets.

Definition: 3.1.3 Let \mathcal{Z} be collection of every eff dominating sets in \mathfrak{B} . Domination number is given by $\gamma_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{\mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{Z}} (\varpi_t(\mathcal{S}), \varpi_i(\mathcal{S}), \varpi_f(\mathcal{S}))$. The dominating set with the least $\gamma_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathfrak{B})$ is eff dominating set \mathcal{S} . The number of elements in \mathcal{S} is denoted by $n(\gamma_{\mathcal{S}})$.

3.2. Effective dominating matrix

Definition:3.2.1 Take $\mathfrak{B}=(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, t, i, f)$ as NovG and $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ as eff dominating set in \mathfrak{B} . The eff dominating matrix of \mathfrak{B} is defined as $\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = [a_{\kappa\omega}]$ where

$$a_{\kappa\sigma} = \begin{cases} (t_{\mathcal{N}}(\kappa\sigma), i_{\mathcal{N}}(\kappa\sigma), f_{\mathcal{N}}(\kappa\sigma)) & \text{if } (\kappa, \sigma) \in \mathcal{N} \\ (1,1,1) & \text{if } \kappa = \sigma \text{ and } \kappa \in \mathcal{S} \\ (0,0,0) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The effective dominating matrix of NovG can be represented by $\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = (t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}), i_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}), f_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))$ where

$$t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \begin{cases} t_{\mathcal{N}}(\kappa\sigma) & \text{if } (\kappa, \sigma) \in \mathcal{N} \\ 1 & \text{if } \kappa = \sigma \text{ and } \kappa \in \mathcal{S}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$i_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \begin{cases} i_{\mathcal{N}}(\kappa\sigma) & \text{if } (\kappa, \sigma) \in \mathcal{N} \\ 1 & \text{if } \kappa = \sigma \text{ and } \kappa \in \mathcal{S} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$f_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \begin{cases} f_{\mathcal{N}}(\kappa\sigma) & \text{if } (\kappa, \sigma) \in \mathcal{N} \\ 1 & \text{if } \kappa = \omega \text{ and } \kappa \in \mathcal{S} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3.3. Effective dominating energy

Definition: 3.3.1 Let $\mathfrak{B}=(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, t, i, f)$ be NovG. Let collection of characteristic values of $t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}), i_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ and $f_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ be ϑ_g, l_g and κ_g respectively. The effective dominating energy of NovG is characterized by

$$\mathcal{E}_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \left(\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})), \mathcal{E}(i_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})), \mathcal{E}(f_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \right)$$

$$= \left(\sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g|, \sum_{g=1}^r |l_g|, \sum_{g=1}^r |\kappa_g| \right)$$

where $\sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g|$ is absolute sum of eigen values of $t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ and $\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))$ is effective dominating energy of $t_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ matrix, $\sum_{g=1}^r |l_g|$ is absolute sum of eigen values of $i_{\mathbb{E}\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ and

$\mathcal{E}(i_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P}))$ is effective dominating energy of $i_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P})$ matrix, $\sum_{g=1}^r |\kappa_g|$ is absolute sum of eigen values of $f_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P})$ and $\mathcal{E}(f_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P}))$ is effective dominating energy of $f_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P})$ matrix.

Example: 3.3.2 Consider NovG $\mathfrak{P}=(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, t, i, f)$ as Fig 1. with $v = \{A, B, C, D, E, F\}$ and $e = \{AB, BC, CD, DE, EF, AF, BE, CF, DF\}$. The effectiveness of edges of \mathfrak{P} is discussed in the below Table 1.

Edges in \mathfrak{P}	t -effective	i -effective	f -effective	Effective
AB	×	√	√	√
BC	×	×	√	√
CD	√	×	√	√
DE	×	×	×	×
EF	×	√	×	√
AF	√	×	√	√
BE	√	√	×	√
CF	√	√	×	√
DF	×	√	×	√

Table 1.

Figure 1.

In \mathfrak{P} , edge DE is not effective since it is neither of t -eff, i -eff and f -eff. The effective edges in \mathfrak{P} are $\{AB, BC, CD, EF, AF, BE, CF, DF\}$. Since $\gamma_S(\mathfrak{P}) = \min_{S \in \mathcal{Z}} (\omega_t(S), \omega_i(S), \omega_f(S)) = 4.2$, eff dominating set with the least $\gamma_S(\mathfrak{P})$ is $S = \{B, F\}$.

Then $\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P})$ is given by

$$\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{G}D^r}(\mathfrak{P}) = \begin{bmatrix} (0,0,0) & (0.2,0.5,1.6) & (0,0,0) & (0,0,0) & (0,0,0) & (0.3,0.2,1.8) \\ (0.2,0.5,1.6) & (1,1,1) & (0.4,0.3,1.3) & (0,0,0) & (0.7,0.5,1.4) & (0,0,0) \\ (0,0,0) & (0.4,0.3,1.3) & (0,0,0) & (0.3,0.5,1.4) & (0,0,0) & (0.5,1.2,0.9) \\ (0,0,0) & (0,0,0) & (0.3,0.5,1.4) & (0,0,0) & (0.1,0.4,1.2) & (0.2,0.8,1.3) \\ (0,0,0) & (0.7,0.5,1.4) & (0,0,0) & (0.1,0.4,1.2) & (0,0,0) & (0.4,0.6,1.4) \\ (0.3,0.2,1.8) & (0,0,0) & (0.5,1.2,0.9) & (0.2,0.8,1.3) & (0.4,0.6,1.4) & (1,1,1) \end{bmatrix}$$

This can also be represented as

$$t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.3 \\ 0.2 & 1 & 0.4 & 0 & 0.7 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.4 & 0 & 0.3 & 0 & 0.5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.3 & 0 & 0.1 & 0.2 \\ 0 & 0.7 & 0 & 0.1 & 0 & 0.4 \\ 0.3 & 0 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.4 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigen values of $t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ are 1.71623,1.07093,-0.71263,-0.188924,0.151033,-0.0366308.

By definition:3.3.1, effective dominating energy of $t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ matrix is given by

$$\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) = \sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g| = 1.71623+1.07093+0.71263+0.188924+0.151033+0.0366308=3.8763778.$$

$$i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.2 \\ 0.5 & 1 & 0.3 & 0 & 0.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.3 & 0 & 0.5 & 0 & 1.2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.5 & 0 & 0.4 & 0.8 \\ 0 & 0.5 & 0 & 0.4 & 0 & 0.6 \\ 0.2 & 0 & 1.2 & 0.8 & 0.6 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigen values of $i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ are 2.44725,1.24647,-1.07308,-0.477629,-0.188631,0.0456269.

By definition:3.3.1, effective dominating energy of $i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ matrix is given by

$$\mathcal{E}(i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) = \sum_{g=1}^r |\iota_g| = 2.44725+1.24647+1.07308+0.477629+0.188631+0.0456269=5.4786869.$$

$$f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1.6 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.8 \\ 1.6 & 1 & 1.3 & 0 & 1.4 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.3 & 0 & 1.4 & 0 & 0.9 \\ 0 & 0 & 1.4 & 0 & 1.2 & 1.3 \\ 0 & 1.4 & 0 & 1.2 & 0 & 1.4 \\ 1.8 & 0 & 0.9 & 1.3 & 1.4 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigen values of $f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ are 4.6112,-0.309616,-1.74119,1.45577,0.786999,-0.0166198.

By definition:3.3.1, effective dominating energy of $f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ matrix is given by

$$\mathcal{E}(f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) = \sum_{g=1}^r |\kappa_g| = 4.6112+0.309616+1.74119+1.45577+0.786999+0.0166198=11.7098688.$$

Therefore, effective dominating energy of NovG is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}) &= (\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})), \mathcal{E}(i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})), \mathcal{E}(f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))) = \left(\sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g|, \sum_{g=1}^r |\iota_g|, \sum_{g=1}^r |\kappa_g| \right) \\ &= (3.8763778, 5.4786869, 11.7098688) \end{aligned}$$

4. Propositions on effective domination in NovG

Proposition: 4.1 Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG and let \mathcal{S} be eff dominating set with $n(\gamma_{\mathcal{S}})$ elements. Let ϑ_g, ι_g and κ_g are eigen values of $t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}), i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ and $f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ respectively. Then

- $\sum_{g=1}^r \vartheta_g = \sum_{g=1}^r \iota_g = \sum_{g=1}^r \kappa_g = n(\gamma_{\mathcal{S}})$
- $\sum_{g=1}^r (\vartheta_g)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < m \leq r} t_{gm} t_{mg}$
- $\sum_{g=1}^r (\iota_g)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r i_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < m \leq r} i_{gm} i_{mg}$
- $\sum_{g=1}^r (\kappa_g)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r f_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < m \leq r} f_{gm} f_{mg}$

Proof:

- Since the trace of matrix $t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ equals the sum of eigenvalues, we obtain

$$\sum_{g=1}^r \vartheta_g = \sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg} = n(\gamma_{\mathcal{S}})$$

In this similar manner we can prove that $\sum_{g=1}^r \iota_g = \sum_{g=1}^r \kappa_g = n(\gamma_{\mathcal{S}})$.

b. Apparently, the total of square of eigen values of $t_{\mathbb{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ equals trace of $(t_{\mathbb{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))^2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence } tr\left((t_{\mathbb{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))^2\right) &= \sum_{g=1}^r (\vartheta_g)^2 \\ &= t_{11}t_{11} + t_{12}t_{21} + \dots + t_{1r}t_{r1} + t_{21}t_{12} + t_{22}t_{22} + \dots + t_{2r}t_{r2} + \dots \\ &\quad + t_{r1}t_{1r} + t_{r2}t_{2r} + \dots + t_{gm}t_{mg} \\ &= \sum_{g=1}^r (\vartheta_g)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < m \leq r} t_{gm}t_{mg} \end{aligned}$$

In the same way $\sum_{g=1}^r (l_g)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r i_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < m \leq r} i_{gm}i_{mg}$ and $\sum_{g=1}^r (\kappa_g)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r f_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < m \leq r} f_{gm}f_{mg}$ can be stated.

Proposition: 4.2 Assume that \mathfrak{B} is a complete NovG such that any two vertices have unique path of length one, which has

- a. t -strength. Then $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{b \in Z} (t_{\mathcal{M}}(b)) + 1$.
- b. i -strength. Then $\gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{b \in Z} (i_{\mathcal{M}}(b)) + 1$.
- c. f -strength. Then $\gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{b \in Z} (f_{\mathcal{M}}(b)) + 1$.
- d. strength. Then $\gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{b \in Z} (t_{\mathcal{M}}(b), i_{\mathcal{M}}(b), f_{\mathcal{M}}(b)) + 1$.

Proof: a. Let \mathfrak{B} be complete NovG. Take any two vertices s and x . Since there is a single path of length one between s and x that has t -strength, path p from s to x takes form $\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}^{\infty}(s, x)_t = \max\{\chi_{\mathfrak{B}}(p)_t\} = t_{\mathcal{N}}(sx)$. Edge sx is hence t -eff. In addition, each vertex being connected to every other vertex and every edge is t -eff. As a result, $S = \{s\}$ is t -eff dominating set. The statement (a) is valid since $\sum_{sx \text{ is } t\text{-eff edge}} t_{\mathcal{N}}(sx) = \sum_{sx \text{ is edge}} t_{\mathcal{N}}(sx) \forall s, x \in v$.

Likewise, the conclusions are valid for b,c and d.

Proposition: 4.3 Consider \mathfrak{B} as \emptyset NovG with \wp being order. Then $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = \wp$.

Proof: Let \mathfrak{B} be \emptyset NovG. Since it lacks t -eff edges, v is t -eff dominating set in \mathfrak{B} . Consequently, $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \min_{S \in Z} (w_t(S)) = \sum_{b \in S} (w_t(b)) = \sum_{b \in V} t_{\mathcal{M}}(b) = \wp$. Therefore, $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \wp$. Making use of definition:3.1.3 in a way similar to this proof, we clearly obtain $\gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = \wp$.

It should be emphasized as below that Proposition:4.3's counterpart will not hold true.

For instance: 4.4

Figure 2.

Consider NovG with edges AB, BC, CD, AD as in Figure 2. Here eff edges are $\{AB, BC, CD\}$ and eff dominating set is $\{A, D\}$. Hence $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = 2.4 = \sum_{b \in v} t_{\mathcal{M}}(b)$, $\gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = 2.7 = \sum_{b \in v} i_{\mathcal{M}}(b)$, $\gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = 3.5 = \sum_{b \in v} f_{\mathcal{M}}(b)$. Therefore $\gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = \wp$ but \mathfrak{B} is not \emptyset NovG.

Proposition: 4.5 Let \mathfrak{R} be spanning subgraph of tree \mathfrak{B} . For edges $kl \in \mathfrak{R}$ the following are equivalent:

- a. t -bridges, i -bridges, f -bridges and bridges of \mathfrak{B}
- b. t -eff, i -eff, f -eff and eff edges of \mathfrak{B}
- c. connected by vertices of t -eff, i -eff, f -eff and eff dominating sets of \mathfrak{B}
- d. $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{R}), \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{R}), \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{R}), \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_S(\mathfrak{R})$

Proof: Let kl be edge in \mathfrak{R} . If kl is not t -bridge, then we can discover t -path from k to l , that does not include kl , such that $\{\chi_{G-kl}^\infty(k, l)_t\} > t_N(kl)$. Since \mathfrak{R} is spanning subgraph, \mathfrak{p} must involve edges outside of \mathfrak{R} . Let $m_1n_1 \notin \mathfrak{R}$ be edge of \mathfrak{p} . Hence m_1n_1 is transformed into t -path p_1 in \mathfrak{R} such that $t_N(m_1n_1) > t_N(kl)$ and p_1 is devoid kl . As before, by replacing an edge $m_1n_1 \in \mathfrak{p}$ which is not in \mathfrak{R} by a path p_i , we acquire t -path in \mathfrak{R} from k to l , not including kl . Because \mathfrak{B} is acyclic, we thus obtain a contradiction. The proof of (a) is thus complete.

Proposition 5.3 in [2] states that (b) emanates from (a). The concept of t -eff, i -eff, f -eff and eff dominating sets of \mathfrak{B} can be implemented to follow verification of (c) and (d), which is analogous to (a) and (b).

Proposition: 4.6 Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG with eff dominating set \mathcal{S} .

- a. $\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \leq \sqrt{r(\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb}t_{bg})}$
- b. $\mathcal{E}(i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \leq \sqrt{r(\sum_{g=1}^r i_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} i_{gb}i_{bg})}$
- c. $\mathcal{E}(f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \leq \sqrt{r(\sum_{g=1}^r f_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} f_{gb}f_{bg})}$

Proof: Applying $a_g = 1$ and $b_g = |\vartheta_g|$ to Cauchy-Schwarz inequality $(\sum_{g=1}^r a_g b_g)^2 \leq (\sum_{g=1}^r a_g^2)(\sum_{g=1}^r b_g^2)$ and by proposition: 4.1,

$$\left(\sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g|\right)^2 \leq \left(\sum_{g=1}^r 1\right)\left(\sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g|^2\right)$$

$$\left(\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))\right)^2 \leq r\left(\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb}t_{bg}\right)$$

$$\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \leq \sqrt{r\left(\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb}t_{bg}\right)}$$

In the same way, we can show (b) and (c).

Proposition: 4.7 Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG with eff dominating set \mathcal{S} . Here $|\mathcal{J}|, |\mathcal{K}|$ and $|\mathcal{L}|$ denote determinants of $t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}), i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ and $f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})$ respectively.

- a. $\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \geq \sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb}t_{bg} + r(r-1)|\mathcal{J}|^{\frac{2}{r}}}$
- b. $\mathcal{E}(i_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \geq \sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^r i_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} i_{gb}i_{bg} + r(r-1)|\mathcal{K}|^{\frac{2}{r}}}$
- c. $\mathcal{E}(f_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) \geq \sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^r f_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} f_{gb}f_{bg} + r(r-1)|\mathcal{L}|^{\frac{2}{r}}}$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\mathcal{E}(t_{\mathfrak{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))\right)^2 &= \left(\sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_g|\right)^2 = \sum_{g=1}^r |\vartheta_{gg}|^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} \vartheta_{gb}\vartheta_{bg} \\ &= \left(\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb}t_{bg}\right) + \frac{2r(r-1)}{2} \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} \{|\vartheta_g||\vartheta_b|\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Since } 1 \leq g < b \leq r \{ |t_g| |t_b| \} &\stackrel{AM}{\geq} 1 \leq g < b \leq r \{ |t_g| |t_b| \} \\
 &= \left(\prod_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} |t_g| |t_b| \right)^{\frac{2}{r(r-1)}} = \left(\prod_{1 \leq g \leq r} |t_g|^{r-1} \right)^{\frac{2}{r(r-1)}} = \left(\prod_{1 \leq g \leq r} |t_g| \right)^{\frac{2}{r}} = |J|^{\frac{2}{r}} \\
 \mathcal{E}(t_{\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B}))^2 &\geq \left(\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb} t_{bg} \right) + r(r-1) |J|^{\frac{2}{r}} \\
 \mathcal{E}(t_{\mathcal{D}^r}(\mathfrak{B})) &\geq \sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^r t_{gg}^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq g < b \leq r} t_{gb} t_{bg} + r(r-1) |J|^{\frac{2}{r}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, we can show (b) and (c).

Proposition:4.8 Let \mathfrak{B} be NovG of order \wp . Then

- a. $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) \leq \wp$
- b. $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) + \gamma_{S_t}(\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{B})), \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) + \gamma_{S_i}(\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{B})), \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) + \gamma_{S_f}(\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{B})), \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) + \gamma_S(\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{B})) \leq 2\wp$

Proof: By proposition:4.3, \exists NovG $\mathfrak{B} \ni \gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}) = \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) = \wp$. Through definition of $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B})$ it must be demonstrated that $\gamma_{S_t}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_{S_i}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_{S_f}(\mathfrak{B}), \gamma_S(\mathfrak{B}) \leq \wp$. Then proof of (b) can be expressed by applying (a) to \mathfrak{B} and $\mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{B})$.

5. Applications

5.1. Effective domination in sports analytics

The idea of domination in NovG can be applied for sports analytics. It integrates decision-making with uncertainty, fuzzy logic, and graph theory, which is highly helpful in intricate, uncertain domains like sports. Despite performance data uncertainty, analysis of player performance is done in order to select a group of players who have a major impact on game outcomes. In addition to determining a player's skill level, NovGs allow team management to assess a player's level of confidence, uncertainty, and bias. The construction of NovG is made such that players are vertices and edges stand for their impact on team which is resulted by the interaction between those two players. Every vertex and edge have a value for (t, i, f) . For example, consider NovG which is constructed by connecting each player to every other player as in Figure 3:

Figure 3.

$t_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbb{E})$: The degree of player \mathbb{E} 's effectiveness in enhancing the team's overall performance during challenging times

$i_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbb{E})$: The degree of player \mathbb{E} 's efficiency in enhancing the team's overall performance that cannot be precisely assessed.

$f_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbb{E})$: The degree of player \mathbb{E} 's inefficiency in enhancing the team's overall performance

$t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbb{CE})$: The impact of players \mathbb{CE} efficiency in achieving sporting success

$i_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbb{CE})$: The impact of players \mathbb{CE} efficiency in achieving success in sports conditions cannot be precisely determined.

$f_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbb{CE})$: The impact of inefficiency of players \mathbb{CE} on achieving sporting success.

In this instance, the concept of effective edges $t_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbb{CE}) > \{\chi^{\infty}_{g-\mathbb{CE}}(\mathbb{C}, \mathbb{E})_t\}$, $i_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbb{CE}) > \{\chi^{\infty}_{g-\mathbb{CE}}(\mathbb{C}, \mathbb{E})_i\}$, $f_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbb{CE}) > \{\chi^{\infty}_{g-\mathbb{CE}}(\mathbb{C}, \mathbb{E})_f\}$ is used to find the strength between two players. Here, we can observe that player \mathbb{D} dominates every other player f -effectively. Hence \mathbb{D} must improve efficiency for achieving success in every events.

5.2. Comparison of NG with NovG

For balanced and practical data analysis, NG works best where uncertainty exists but is managed. NovG excels in dramatic or contradictory situations that are frequently found in sports storylines. NG in player performance evaluation stands for ambiguous player evaluations, while NovG permits modelling of players with a significant review score. For instance, determine if Player X ought to be in the final starting lineup. The final decision comprises the idea of medical staff (1.2,0.8,0.3) indicating the player is medically fit above what is required, and coach decision (0.6,1.1,0.2) which indicates the player X has substantial uncertainty. In order to incorporate various, frequently conflicting stakeholder viewpoints regarding Player X's preparedness for the championship final, we use a NovG. Neutrosophic Over Graphs are a potent tool for simulating reality as it is, complete with contradictions, emotions, extremes, and uncertainties. This is particularly true in the highly emotive realm of sports. They serve as instruments for decision-making in the high-stakes and imperfect environments of sports, in addition to being mathematically expressive.

6. Conclusions

This article presents and explains the idea of effective dominating energy in NovG with an example. Further, the properties of eigen values of effective dominating matrix, bounds for effective dominating energy and propositions on effective domination in NovG are discussed. Finally, an application of effective domination in sports analytics using NovG is elaborated.

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